

UDC 342.9:343.62

Maryana Kachynska, –

Ph.D, associate professor

police activity and public administration department of

Kharkiv National University of Internal Affairs

(27 Lva Landau Av., Kharkiv, Ukraine)

Administrative Liability for Animal Cruelty: the Experience of Ukraine

Стаття присвячена питанню адміністративної відповідальності за жорстоке поводження із тваринами: досвід України. У статті розкрита поява засад захисту тварин в Україні. У статті розглянуто національне правове регулювання попередження та протидії жорстокому поводженню із тваринами. Автор детально аналізує правовий статус тварини відповідно до норм чинного законодавства України. Окремо розглянуто адміністративна відповідність за жорстоке поводження із тваринами, особливості притягнення до адміністративної відповідальності за жорстоке поводження з тваринами неповнолітніх.

Ключові слова: *жорстоке поводження із тваринами, міжнародні договори у сфері добробуту тварин, національне законодавство України щодо попередження та протидії жорстокому поводженню із тваринами, склад адміністративного правопорушення, що передбачене ст. 89 Кодексу України про адміністративні правопорушення, особливості відповідальності дітей за неналежне поводження з тваринами, правовий статус тварини в Україні.*

Статья посвящена вопросу административной ответственности за жестокое обращение с животными: опыт Украины. В статье указано, что появление основ защиты животных. В статье рассмотрены национальное правовое регулирование предупреждения и противодействия жестокому обращению с животными. Автор подробно анализирует правовой устав животные соответствии с нормами действующего законодательства Украины. Отдельно рассмотрены административная соответствии за жестокое обращение с животными, особенности привлечения к административной ответственности за жестокое обращение с животными несовершеннолетних.

Ключевые слова: *жестокое обращение с животными, международные договоры в сфере благополучия животных, национальное законодательство Украины относительно предупреждения и противодействия жестокому обращению с животными, состав административного правонарушения, предусмотренное ст. 89 Кодекса Украины об административных правонарушениях, особенности ответственности детей за ненадлежащее обращение с животными, правовой статус животных в Украине.*

The article is devoted to the issue of administrative liability for cruelty to animals: the experience of Ukraine. The article states that factors such as the emergence of humanistic principles of societal organization led to a rethinking the world's existence, animals and people in it. The result was the concept of protecting the natural rights of animals. Today, the issue of animal protection is given considerable attention at the international and national levels.

The author examines international agreements in the field of animal welfare, which Ukraine has joined and ratified. The article considers the national legal regulation of prevention and counteraction to animal cruelty. The author analyses in detail the legal status of animals in accordance with current Ukrainian legislation. It is noted that animals in Ukraine are equated with a 'special status' thing, namely the property rights of animals' owners are limited by legislation on the protection of animals from cruel treatment.

Administrative liability for cruelty to animals is considered separately. The author analysed in detail the composition of the offense, which is provided by Article 89 of the Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses.

Special attention is paid to the peculiarities of bringing to administrative responsibility for ill-treatment of minors. The peculiarities of the administrative qualification of non-fulfilment by parents of parental

responsibilities for the upbringing of a child who committed cruelty to animals aged 14 to 16 years are analysed.

Keywords: *animal cruelty, international treaties in the field of animal welfare, national legislation of Ukraine on prevention and counteraction to animal cruelty, the composition of an administrative offense under Article 89 of the Code of Administrative Offenses of Ukraine, features of children's liability for improper treatment of animals, legal animal status in Ukraine.*

Addressing the problem. The emergence of humanistic principles of organization of society, as well as a number of other factors, led to a rethinking of the idea of the existence of the world, animals and people in it. The result was the concept of protecting the natural rights of animals. Today, the issue of animal protection is given considerable attention at the international and national levels.

Analysis of research and publications. The issue of preventing and combating animal cruelty has been the subject of research by many scientists, namely: M. Appleby, D. Broom, M. Bowman, D. Zhuravlyov, N. Zubchenko and others. The relationship of animal cruelty with other marginal behavior of persons, namely domestic violence, child abuse has been studied in the works of such international scientists as E. Alleyne, F. Acro, B. Blonska, J. Zorza, M. Zinley, N. Taylor, A. Fijerald, S. Parfitt and others.

Previously unsolved problems. However, due to the improvement of the national legislation of Ukraine in the field of protection of animal rights, changes in the legal responsibility for cruelty to animals, there are a number of aspects that need further study. The above determines the relevance of the study of administrative liability for animal cruelty.

Basic content. Today it is common knowledge that 'humane attitudes' are one of the main criteria for determining the civilization of society [1, p.46]. At the international level, most countries reaffirm their commitment to humane treatment of animals, as a result of which a number of international agreements have been concluded in the field of animal protection, namely: the European Convention for the Protection of Pets [2]; European Convention for the protection of vertebrate animals used for research and other scientific purposes [3]; Convention on the Conservation of Migratory Species of Wild Animals [4]; United Nations Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) [5]; Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-Making and Access to

Justice in Environmental Matters (Aarhus Convention) [6]; Convention on Biological Diversity [7]; Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety to the Convention on Biological Diversity [8]; Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora [9]; Agreement on the Conservation of Afro-Eurasian Migratory Wetlands [10]; Convention on the Conservation of European Wildlife and Natural Habitats [11] and others.

The **Basic Law** is the main national legal normative document, which lays down the principles of legal regulation not only in the field of prevention, counteraction to animal cruelty, but also in the state system in general. According to Art. 66 of the **Constitution of Ukraine**, everyone is obliged not to cause damage to nature and to compensate for the damage caused by it. The principles of use of natural resources are determined exclusively by the laws of Ukraine (paragraph 5 of Article 92 of the Basic Law) [12].

The issue of animal protection is regulated by a number of normative documents, including the Law of Ukraine "On Protection of Animals from Cruelty" [13]. However, it should be noted that the effectiveness of this law and current legislation on the protection of animals from cruel treatment is not high enough. The reasons for this include:

- Unfortunately, legal nihilism is present in the post-Soviet space;
- Understanding of the protection of animal rights as a secondary and unimportant phenomenon, especially by public administration bodies in general and the police, courts, prosecutors in particular;
- Imperfection of the current legislation in the field of animal protection [14, p.198].

In accordance with paragraph 1 of Article 180 of *The Civil Code of Ukraine*, **animals have the legal status of a thing and they are a special object of civil rights** [15]. **The right of ownership or other real rights of the person keeping the animal are limited by the obligation to comply with the norms and requirements of the Law of Ukraine "On Protection of Animals from Cruelty"**

(Article 12) [13]. The right of ownership and other real rights to animals **in case of cruel treatment may be terminated by a court decision by their seizure or confiscation for a fee.**

According to the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "**On Protection of Animals from Cruelty**", **animal abuse** - is mistreatment abuse of animals, including homeless ones, which caused torture, physical suffering, bodily injury, mutilation or death, incitement of animals to one and the other animals, committed for hooligan or selfish motives, leaving domestic and farm animals at random, including violations of the rules of keeping animals [13].

In the **Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses** (hereinafter - KUpAP) the legislator provided a special rule establishing liability for cruelty to animals, namely in **Article 89** recognized as an offense:

- *animal abuse* - abuse of animals, beatings or other acts of violence that caused the animal physical pain, suffering and did not cause bodily harm, injury or death, *leaving animals at random*, including *violations of the rules of keeping animals*;

- the same acts committed against two or more animals, or by a group of persons, or by a person who has been subject to an administrative penalty during the year for the same offense,

- *propaganda of animal abuse*;

- *violence against animals aimed at satisfying sexual desire* [16].

The subject of this offense is an individual who has reached 16 years of age. Note that if a person aged 14-16 years treats an animal cruelly, or commits other acts provided for in Article 89 of the Code of Administrative Offenses, it will not be held administratively liable. However, it should be borne in mind that in this case, the child's parents will be held administratively liable under Art. 189 "Failure of parents or persons replacing them, responsibilities for the upbringing of children" KUpAP.

The subjective side of animal cruelty is expressed in the form of intent, i.e. the person is aware of the socially dangerous nature of his action (action or inaction), foresaw its socially dangerous consequences and wanted them to occur.

The object of this offense **are public relations in the field of wildlife protection, natural animal rights**. The latter arise in accordance with the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On

Protection of Animals from Cruelty" which states that this law is aimed at protection from suffering and death of animals due to cruel treatment, protection of their natural rights and strengthening morality and humanity of society [13]. **The immediate object** is the established procedure for handling animals. **The object of encroachment** - is an animal that is at large, including homeless, in semi-free conditions or kept in captivity.

The objective side of the offense under Article 89 of the Code of Administrative Offenses is expressed in the following forms:

1. cruel treatment of animals;

2. leaving animals at random;

3. violation of the rules of keeping animals;

4. propaganda of animal cruelty;

5. violence against animals aimed at satisfying sexual desire.

In Article 7 of the Law of Ukraine "On Prevention of Cruelty to Animals", the legislator indicates the general rules for **keeping animals, which exclude cruelty**, namely:

- the conditions of keeping animals must correspond to their biological, species and individual characteristics;

- the conditions of keeping animals must meet their natural needs for food, water, sleep, movement, contact with their peers, natural activity and other needs;

- the number of kept animals is limited by the possibility of providing them with housing conditions in accordance with the requirements of the legislation;

- the place of keeping animals must be equipped in such a way as to provide the necessary space, temperature and humidity, natural light, ventilation and the possibility of contact of animals with their natural environment;

- keeping animals in children's institutions is allowed provided that constant care of animals is provided in accordance with the legislation [13].

When handling animals is not allowed:

- use of equipment, inventory, injuring animals;

- forcing animals to perform actions that are unnatural for them, leading to injuries;

- beatings, injuries in order to force animals to comply with any requirements;

- use of animals in conditions of excessive physiological loads, etc.[13].

A pet can be accompanied by a person who has reached 14 years of age [13].

The Law of Ukraine "On Protection of Animals from Cruelty" applies to the following activities: livestock, including breeding livestock; treatment of animals on the territory of state nature reserves, on the territory of other specially protected natural territories; hunting, hunting economy, fishing; keeping pets and breeding work with them; use of animals in circuses, zoos, exhibitions and other entertainment events; use of animals in sports, in the field of recreation and entertainment of people; use of animals for research and educational purposes, in testing; use of animals in production, including in production of biological preparations; other activities where the impact on animals [17, p.185].

Administrative liability for the offenses specified in Article 89 of the Code of Administrative Offenses is provided in the form of imposition of administrative penalties, namely:

- Under Part 1 of this article - entail the imposition of a fine of 200 to 300 non-taxable minimum incomes, with confiscation of the animal, if the stay of the animal with the owner is a threat to his life or health;

- Under Part 2 - entail the imposition of a fine of 300 to 500 non-taxable minimum incomes or administrative arrest for up to 15 days with confiscation of the animal, if the stay of the animal with the owner is a threat to his life or health;

- Part 3 entails the imposition of a fine of 200 to 500 tax-free minimum incomes with confiscation of the animal, if the stay of the animal with the owner is a threat to his life or health [16].

It should be borne in mind that the legal regulation of the prevention and combating of cruelty to animals is also carried out through a number of by-laws. The procedure for registration of materials in the case of administrative offenses in the field of animal protection is regulated by **The order of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine dated 06.11.2015 № 1376 "On approval of the Instruction on registration of materials on administrative offenses in the police"** [18].

Summarizing the above, we can indicate the following. Today, Ukraine is carrying out reform processes on the way to the EU in all spheres of state life. The protection of animal rights is no exception. Accession to international agreements in the field of animal protection, bringing national legislation into line with EU requirements and standards in the field of animal welfare create the preconditions for improving the situation with animal protection. However, this process cannot be considered complete and requires painstaking work on the part of the authorities. The introduction of not only administrative and criminal liability for cruelty to animals, but also the implementation of comprehensive state programs for the prevention of this offense, educating young people in the spirit of humane treatment of animals will help to overcome legal nihilism and indifference of society to cruelty, not only to animals but also to people.

Список використаних джерел:

1. Турська В. О. Історичний аспект адміністративно-правового регулювання протидії жорстокого поводження із тваринами. *Наше право*. 2014. №6. С. 46-51
2. Європейська конвенція про захист домашніх тварин. Міжнародний документ від 13.11.1987. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/994_a15.
3. Європейська конвенція про захист хребетних тварин, що використовуються для дослідних та інших наукових цілей. Міжнародний документ від 18.03.1986. URL : https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/994_137
4. Конвенція про збереження мігруючих видів диких тварин. Міжнародний документ від 23.06.1979. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_136.
5. Конвенція ООН про міжнародну торгівлю видами дикої фауни та флори, що перебувають під загрозою зникнення. Міжнародний документ від 03.03.1973. URL : https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_129.
6. Конвенція про доступ до інформації, участь громадськості в процесі прийняття рішень та доступ до правосуддя з питань, що стосуються довкілля. Міжнародний документ від 25.06.1998. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/994_015.

7. Конвенція про охорону біологічного різноманіття. Міжнародний документ від 05.06.1992. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_030.
8. Картахенський протокол про біобезпеку до Конвенції про біологічне різноманіття. Міжнародний документ від 29.01.2000. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_935.
9. Конвенція про міжнародну торгівлю видами дикої флори та фауни, що перебувають під загрозою зникнення. Міжнародний документ від 03.03.1973. URL : https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_129.
10. Угода про збереження афро-євразійських мігруючих водно-болотних птахів. Міжнародний документ від 16.06.1995. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/card/en/995_934.
11. Конвенція про охорону дикої флори та фауни і природних середовищ існування в Європі. Міжнародний документ від 19.09.1979. URL : https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/card/995_032.
12. Конституція України. Закон України від 28.06.1996 року. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/254%D0%BA/96-%D0%B2%D1%80>.
13. Про захист тварин від жорстокого поводження. Закон України від 21.02.2006 року. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3447-15>.
14. Зубченко Н.І. Міжнародно-правове співробітництво у сфері забезпечення добробуту тварин та їх захист від жорстокого поводження: монографія / під ред. Т.Р. Короткого. Одеса: Фенікс, 2016. 284 с.
15. Цивільний кодекс України. Закон України від 16.01.2003 року. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/435-15/ed20200704>.
16. Кодекс України про адміністративні правопорушення: кодекс України від 07 грудня 1984 року №8073-Х. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/80731-10>.
17. Науково-практичний коментар Кодексу України про адміністративні правопорушення / за заг. ред. Журавльова Д.В. Київ: Видавничий дім «Професіонал», 2019. 800 с.
18. Про затвердження Інструкції з оформлення матеріалів про адміністративні правопорушення в органах поліції. Наказ МВС України від 06.11.2015 № 1376. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z1496-15#Text>.

References:

1. Turska V. O. Istorychnyi aspekt administratyvno-pravovoho rehuliuвання protydii zhorstokoho povodzhennia iz tvarynamy. *Nashe pravo*. 2014. №6. S. 46-51.
2. Yevropeiska konventsiiia pro zakhyst domashnikh tvaryn. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 13.11.1987. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/994_a15.
3. Yevropeiska konventsiiia pro zakhyst khrebetnykh tvaryn, shcho vykorystovuiutsia dlia doslidnykh ta inshykh naukovykh tsilei. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 18.03.1986. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/994_137.
4. Konventsiiia pro zberezhenntia mihruuiuchykh vydiv dykykh tvaryn. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 23.06.1979. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_136.
5. Konventsiiia OON pro mizhнародnu torhivliu vydamy dykoi fauny ta flory, shcho перебуvaiut pid zahrozoiu znyknennia. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 03.03.1973. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_129.
6. Konventsiiia pro dostup do informatsii, uchast hromadskosti v protsesi pryiniattia rishen ta dostup do pravosuddia z pytan, shcho stosuiutsia dovkillia. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 25.06.1998. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/994_015.
7. Konventsiiia pro okhoronu biolohichnoho riznomanittia. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 05.06.1992. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_030.
8. Kartakhenskyi protokol pro biobezpeku do Konventsii pro biolohichne riznomanittia. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 29.01.2000. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_935.
9. Konventsiiia pro mizhнародnu torhivliu vydamy dykoi flory ta fauny, shcho перебуvaiut pid zahrozoiu znyknennia. Mizhнародnyi dokument vid 03.03.1973. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/995_129.

10. Uhoda pro zberezhennia afro-ievraziiskykh mihruichykh vodno-bolotnykh ptakhiv. Mizhnarodnyi dokument vid 16.06.1995. URL: https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/card/en/995_934.

11. Konventsiiia pro okhoronu dykoi flory ta fauny i pryrodnykh seredovyshch isnuvannia v Yevropi. Mizhnarodnyi dokument vid 19.09.1979. URL : https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/card/995_032.

12. Konstytutsiia Ukrainy. Zakon Ukrainy vid 28.06.1996 roku. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/254%D0%BA/96-%D0%B2%D1%80>.

13. Pro zakhyst tvaryn vid zhorstokoho povodzhennia. Zakon Ukrainy vid 21.02.2006 roku. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3447-15>.

14. Zubchenko N.I. Mizhnarodno-pravove spivrobitnytstvo u sferi zabezpechennia dobrobutu tvaryn ta yikh zakhyst vid zhorstokoho povodzhennia: monohrafiia / pid red. T.R. Korotkoho. Odesa: Feniks, 2016. 284 s.

15. Tsyvilnyi kodeks Ukrainy. Zakon Ukrainy vid 16.01.2003 roku. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/435-15/ed20200704>.

16. Kodeks Ukrainy pro administratyvni pravoporushennia: kodeks Ukrainy vid 07 hrudnia 1984 roku №8073-Kh. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/80731-10>.

17. Naukovo-praktychnyi komentar Kodeksu Ukrainy pro administratyvni pravoporushennia / za zah. red. Zhuravlova D.V. Kyiv: Vydavnychiy dim «Profesional», 2019. 800 s.

18. Pro zatverdzhennia Instruksii z oformlennia materialiv pro administratyvni pravoporushennia v orhanakh politsii. Nakaz MVS Ukrainy vid 06.11.2015 № 1376. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z1496-15#Text>.